

Capítulo 1

Guia Referencial Prático

O objetivo do guia referencial proposto é auxiliar os desenvolvedores de software a escolher a ferramenta de teste mais adequada de acordo com o cenário em que melhor se enquadra. O guia é dividido em quatro partes especializadas em uma determinada área de teste (API; Mobile; Desktop; Web), cada área seleciona e organiza as ferramentas de teste mais relevantes as separando por tipos de teste (Functional; Regression; UI; Load) e por preço (Open source; Commercial). Dessa forma é possível rapidamente identificar quais ferramentas são recomendadas para cada cenário específico. Em seguida, apresenta-se uma tabela comparativa indicando informações úteis acerca das ferramentas da área de forma a auxiliar o usuário a escolher a ferramenta que melhor se enquadra ao seu caso específico dentre as recomendadas.

De forma simples, o usuário primeiro identifica as ferramentas recomendadas de acordo com a sua área, tipo de teste e preço e em seguida compara as ferramentas encontradas na tabela de forma a encontrar a ferramenta mais adequada para seu projeto atual. O guia é apresentado nas Figuras 1.1, 1.2, 1.3, e 1.4 e complementado pelas Tabelas 1.1, 1.2, 1.3 e 1.4

Figura 1.1: Guia prático: API Testing

	Soap UI	Katalon	Postman
Ease of Learning	Basic features are easy to use, more complex scenarios require a deeper understanding of the tool	Entry-level knowledge to Java/Groovy for debugging	Easy for developers and testers to understand and navigate the tool
Community Support	Vibrant community, with numerous forums and resources available for help and guidance	Weak support	Large and active community of users and developers

Record-Playback	Does not support	The Web Recorder Utility function captures actions being performed on the application and converts them into executable code in the back-end	Does not support
Scripting language	Groovy and JavaScript	Groovy	JavaScript
Report generation	Has inbuilt feature to generate reports after the test execution. The report document presents number of test cases, test passed and failed in the report along with the test graphs	Presents analytic results in the form of built-in reports that can be exported in PDF, HTML, Excel, or CSV formats	API documentation includes complete API, path, and operation information, such as authentication methods, parameters, request bodies, response bodies and headers, and examples
API Requests	SOAP/WSDL, REST, GraphQL, JMS	REST: Swagger, OpenAPI 3.0 & WADL, SOAP (SOAP 1.1 & 1.2), GraphQL, Authentication: Basic, Bearer, OAuth 1.0, OAuth 2.0, and NTLM	HTTP, REST, SOAP, GraphQL & WebSockets. Authentication: OAuth 1.2/2.0, AWS Signature, Hawk
	JMeter	TestComplete	LoadRunner
Ease of Learning	GUI is user-friendly. Advanced features and concepts can have a steep learning curve	Relatively steep learning curve	Steep learning curve

Community Support	Has a vibrant community that has developed a wide range of plugins to extend its functionality	Has an active and supportive user community	Strong community and professional support
Record-Playback	Supports record and replay option, the recorded scenario can be edited using JavaScript. The Blazemeter plugin can further be used for editing the recorded script to modify the test case.	Allows record and play back HTTP requests	Support. Captures the application operations based on protocols
Scripting language	Groovy, Beansheel, Javascript, Java	JavaScript	C
Report generation	Provides various built-in listeners and reporting tools that help analyze test results and identify performance bottlenecks	Provides visual logs and test execution results. Offers detailed reports with screenshots and test coverage information, aiding in test analysis	Provides graphical representation of results through LoadRunner Analysis
API Requests	HTTP, HTTPS, FTP, JDBC, SOAP, REST, WebSocket	REST	HTTP, HTTPS

Tabela 1.1: Ferramentas recomendadas para teste API

Figura 1.2: Guia prático: Mobile Testing

	Appium	Katalon	Robot	TestComplete
Ease of Learning	Requires a certain level of programming knowledge in order to design the test scripts correctly	Easy for testers with little to no coding experience to create and run automated tests	Basic features are easy to use, more complex scenarios require a deeper understanding of the tool	Relatively steep learning curve
Community Support	Large and active community of users and developers	Weak support	Has a wide range of libraries available but some specific or niche libraries may have limited community support	Has an active and supportive user community

Record-Playback	Has an Appium Inspector tool to record and playback. It records and plays native application behavior by inspecting DOM and generates the test script	It has a very simple and easy-to-use interface. Easily capture elements, edit a recorded test, or re-use it to create more automated test cases	Does not have any built-in recorder utility	Script-free record and replay tool allows for recording multi-touch gestures (swipe, pinch, drag, drop, or scroll) and playing them back
Language support	Java, Ruby, Python, C#, JavaScript, PHP	Java, Groovy	Own domain-specific language (DSL). Python, Java, JavaScript	JavaScript, Python
Report generation	Does not have built-in reporting capabilities and requires additional tools to generate reports	Reports are easy to read while also consisting all the important details needed to know in case of test fails	Generates detailed reports and logs automatically, providing visibility into test execution results	Provides reporting capabilities that allow view and export detailed reports
Platforms	iOS, Android, Tizen, Native application, Web mobile, Hybrid	Android, iOS, Native application, Web mobile, Hybrid	Android, iOS, Native application, Web mobile, Hybrid	Android, iOS, Native application, Web mobile, Hybrid
	Ranorex	JMteter	LoadRunner	
Ease of Learning	User-friendly, can be used by any testing team and organisation	GUI is user-friendly. Advanced features and concepts can have a steep learning curve	Steep learning curve	

Community Support	Community support is not as extensive as some open-source tools	Has a vibrant community that has developed a wide range of plugins to extend its functionality	Strong community and professional support	
Record-Playback	Offers many low-code features including capture-and-replay functionality to record tests	Doesn't have a built-in record-and-playback feature. It provides a proxy server component called the "HTTP(S) Test Script Recorder" that allows to record HTTP requests	LoadRunner's Mobile Protocol can record the interactions of a mobile application and later replay those interactions to simulate multiple virtual users accessing the application simultaneously	
Language support	C#, VB.net,	Java	VuGen (Virtual User Generator) script, it is specific to LoadRunner	
Report generation	Provides detailed reports after test execution, including information about test results, screenshots, and logs	Generates HTML report that provides detailed information about response times, throughput, error rates, and more	Generates detailed reports to analyze the results and identify performance bottlenecks	

Platforms	Android, iOS, Native application, Web mobile, Hybrid	Android (with plugins)	iOS, Android	
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Tabela 1.2: Ferramentas recomendadas para teste móvel

Figura 1.3: Guia prático: Desktop Testing

	Katalon	Robot Framework	TestComplete
Ease of Learning	Easy for testers with little to no coding experience to create and run automated tests	Basic features are easy to use, more complex scenarios require a deeper understanding of the tool	Relatively steep learning curve
Community Support	Weak support	Has a wide range of libraries available but some specific or niche libraries may have limited community support	Has an active and supportive user community

Record-Playback	Does not provide native record and playback functionality	Does not have any built-in recorder utility	Offers a record and playback feature, allowing testers to record their interactions with an application and generate test scripts automatically
Language support	Java, Groovy	Own domain-specific language (DSL). Python, Java, C#	Python, JavaScript
Report generation	Reports are easy to read while also consisting all the important details needed to know in case of test fails	Generates detailed reports and logs automatically, providing visibility into test execution results	Provides reporting capabilities that allow view and export detailed reports
Platforms	Windows	Windows, Linux, MAC	Windows
	Ranorex Studio	Apache JMeter	
Ease of Learning	User-friendly, can be used by any testing team and organisation	Steep Learning Curve	
Community Support	Community support is not as extensive as some open-source tools	Has a vibrant community that has developed a wide range of plugins to extend its functionality	

Record-Playback	Fully interchangeable and modifiable recording and coding modules. Capture entire workflows for replay or convert actions to user code and modify it	Doesn't have a built-in record-and-playback feature. It provides a proxy server component called the "HTTP(S) Test Script Recorder" that allows to record HTTP requests	
Language support	C#, VB.net	BeanShell	
Report generation	Fully customizable reports with screenshots, text, and videos	Provides various built-in listeners and reporting tools that help to analyze test results and identify performance bottlenecks	
Platforms	Windows	Windows, Linux, MAC	

Tabela 1.3: Ferramentas recomendadas para teste de desktop

Figura 1.4: Guia prático: Web Testing

	Selenium	Cypress	Katalon	Robot
Ease of Learning	Challenging	Easy to learn	Easy for testers with little to no coding experience to create and run automated tests	Basic features are easy to use, more complex scenarios require a deeper understanding of the tool
Community Support	Large and active community of users and developers	Has a strong and active community support	Weak support	Has a wide range of libraries available but some specific or niche libraries may have limited community support

Record-Playback	Selenium IDE records test runs and exports the recording into TestNG or JUnit test cases	Does not have a traditional record-and-playback feature	Supports. Provides a browser extension that facilitates the recording of interactions with web elements	Does not have any built-in recorder utility. Its necessary to install third-party browser extension
Language support	Java, PHP, C#, Python, Groovy, Ruby, Perl	JavaScript	Java, Groovy	Own domain-specific language (DSL). Python, Java, JavaScript
Report generation	Does not have its own built-in reporting tool	HtmlReport generation using Mocha	Reports are easy to read while also consisting all the important details needed to know in case of test fails	Generates detailed reports and logs automatically, providing visibility into test execution results
Browsers support	Chrome, Firefox, Internet Explorer, Edge, Safari	Chrome, Edge	Chrome, Firefox, Edge, Safari	Chrome, Firefox, Internet Explorer, Edge
	TestComplete	Ranorex Studio	Jmeter	
Ease of Learning	Relatively steep learning curve	User-friendly, can be used by any testing team and organisation	Steep Learning Curve	
Community Support	Has an active and supportive user community	Community support is not as extensive as some open-source tools	Has a vibrant community that has developed a wide range of plugins to extend its functionality	

Record-Playback	Offers a record and playback feature, allowing testers to record their interactions with an application and generate test scripts automatically	Fully interchangeable and modifiable recording and coding modules. Capture entire workflows for replay or convert actions to user code and modify it	Doesn't have a built-in record-and-playback feature. It provides a proxy server component called the "HTTP(S) Test Script Recorder" that allows to record HTTP requests	
Language support	Python, JavaScript	C#, VB.net	BeanShell	
Report generation	Provides reporting capabilities that allow view and export detailed reports	Provides detailed reports after test execution, including information about test results, screenshots, and logs	Provides various built-in listeners and reporting tools that help to analyze test results and identify performance bottlenecks	
Browsers support	Chrome, Firefox, Internet Explorer, Edge, Safari	Chrome, Firefox, Safari, Edge	Primarily operates at the protocol level and is not tied to specific browsers	

Tabela 1.4: Ferramentas recomendadas para teste web